

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

MILITARY COOPERATION: A CRUCIAL PILLAR OF VIETNAMESE - RUSSIAN RELATIONS

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Abstract

The Russian Federation served as a strategic ally of Vietnam for four decades (1950–1990). It was the primary provider of defense aid that assisted Vietnam during the Indochina War and the border conflict with China. Following the collapse of the socialist state in Russia in 1991, the Russian government maintained diplomatic relations with Hanoi, eventually upgrading the relationship to a comprehensive strategic partnership encompassing politics, economics, culture, education, science and technology, and defense and security. This article outlines the defense cooperation between Vietnam and Russia as a crucial pillar of the diplomatic relationship between Hanoi and the Kremlin. It offers a condensed historical overview of Vietnamese-Russian defense collaboration, highlighting the strong historical context of their strategic alliance during the Indochina conflict. The article also focuses on the arms trade and military cooperation agreements between Vietnam and Russia in recent decades, shedding light on the scope and achievements of their defense partnership.

Keywords: crucial pillar, military cooperation, relations, Russian, Vietnam.

1. INTRODUCTION

The friendly cooperation between Vietnam and Russia dates back to when the Cold War intensified into a hotspot in Indochina. During the Indochina War, the Soviet Union, as a major power within the socialist bloc, established diplomatic relations with and provided active support to Vietnam, becoming its close ally. After the Cold War ended, the Russian Federation continued to maintain friendly cooperative relations, particularly in the field of economics, solidifying its role as a "cornerstone" of the bilateral relationship. Today, Russia is one of twelve countries with which Vietnam has established a comprehensive strategic partnership — a group that also includes major powers such as China, India, and the United States (M.O.F.A., 1980).

Vietnam–Russia comprehensive strategic partnership covers a wide range of cooperation areas, including political and diplomatic collaboration, economic cooperation (trade, investment, energy), cultural, tourism, education and training exchanges, defense and security partnerships, scientific and technological cooperation, and the resolution of issues related to the Vietnamese community living in Russia. Numerous legal agreements have been signed to support this partnership, with military cooperation standing out as a vital pillar. Vietnam remains one of Russia's largest markets for military equipment, and Moscow continues to be the leading supplier of arms to Vietnam. In addition, the two countries have engaged in strategic dialogues and maintained exchanges in military science and technology, including military technology transfer, for many years.

Vietnamese-Russian defense cooperation has developed within the broader framework of Vietnam's efforts to build and consolidate the principle of "independence and self-reliance" while implementing a policy of "diversification and multilateralization" in its international relations. Vietnam consistently upholds the principle of safeguarding national interests based on

fundamental tenets of international law, equality, mutual benefit, and the consistent pursuit of an independent, self-reliant, peaceful, cooperative, and development-oriented foreign policy. This strategy also emphasizes proactive and active international integration and Vietnam's readiness to be a trusted partner and responsible member of the international community (C.P.V., 2016). Vietnam employs multilateral cooperation strategies as an approach to engage major powers, maintain strategic balance among them, and avoid aligning with one country against another (Kuik, 2008). Vietnam's multilateral foreign policy approach aligns with the tenets of neoclassical realism, which posits that a state's foreign policy is shaped by its position within the international system, and its capacity for action depends largely on its domestic skills and capabilities (Kozub-Karkut, 2014).

2. A CONCISE HISTORY OF MILITARY COOPERATION IN VIETNAMESE-RUSSIAN RELATIONS BEFORE 1991

The Democratic Republic of Vietnam was proclaimed on September 2, 1945. In November 1950, Vietnam called upon the governments of the world to establish diplomatic relations and to support its resistance against French colonialism and U.S. intervention in the Indochinese Peninsula. China was the first country to recognize and establish diplomatic relations with Vietnam on January 18, 1950, followed by the Soviet Union on January 30, 1950 (Ha, 2024). Vietnam's establishment of diplomatic ties with Russia coincided with the escalation of the Indochina War, fueled by strong U.S. involvement. To avoid direct conflict with U.S. interests in Europe, the Soviet Union provided military aid to Vietnam indirectly through China. Beginning in February 1950, the Soviet Union supplied military aid to China, which then transferred it to Vietnam. With Soviet support, from February to June 1950, more than 3,000 Vietnamese military personnel were sent to China for cultural education and military training.

These personnel were drawn from units such as the 306th Division, the 174th Regiment, the 209th Regiment, one mountain artillery regiment, two combat engineer battalions, and the Military Officer Academy. Starting in July 1952, Vietnam's first heavy artillery regiment, the 45th, underwent training in Yunnan (China), and the 367th Air Defense Regiment received training in Guangxi (China). The equipment and weapons for these two units were supplied by the Soviet Union, while China was responsible for providing training and technical instruction on the use of these Soviet-supplied arms (G.D.O.L., 1995).

With the support of the Soviet Union, Soviet and Chinese experts helped boost morale, and guided the use of military equipment, technology, and combat tactics, thereby contributing to strengthening the combat power of the Vietnam People's Army. As early as 1950, the Soviet Union provided Vietnam with non-repayable aid consisting of strategically significant items, including 37mm anti-aircraft guns, several transport vehicles, and military medicine, transported via China into Vietnam. In 1952, Vietnam requested 10 tons of malaria medication (quinine) from the Soviet Union; the Soviets promptly sent 500 kilograms. That same year, Vietnam requested aid from the Soviet Union consisting of 37mm anti-aircraft guns for four regiments (144 guns and 10 basic loads of ammunition per gun), 72 units of 76.2mm artillery with 10 basic loads of ammunition per gun, 200 units of 12.7mm anti-aircraft guns with ammunition, and training for 50–100 Vietnamese military technical officers. The Soviet Union promptly met Vietnam's requests (Giap, 1995).

Overall, between May 1950 and June 1954, Vietnam received 21,517 tons of aid (including 4,253 tons of weapons and ammunition, 73 tons of military equipment, 5,069 tons of transport goods, 9,590 tons of rice, 1,505 tons of military supplies, 157 tons of medical supplies, 200 tons of communications equipment, 40 tons of engineering supplies; 715 transport trucks; 24 units of 105mm artillery and 1,000 shells; 48 units of 75mm artillery and 32,484 shells; 76 units of 37mm anti-aircraft guns and 51,620 rounds) from the Soviet Union and China, totaling 54 million rubles. Among the weaponry, the entire batch of 37mm anti-aircraft guns (76 guns and accompanying ammunition), all Katyusha rocket launchers (12 six-tube launchers and accompanying rockets), all K50 submachine guns and ammunition, 685 out of 715 transport vehicles, and a large quantity of antibiotics were supplied by the Soviet Union (Hoa, 2013).

After the First Indochina War (1954), Vietnam was divided into two regions with two different governments. North Vietnam became independent and began building a socialist state, while South Vietnam established the Saigon government under U.S. patronage. Subsequently, the Second Indochina War broke out.

At the onset of the Second Indochina War, the Soviet Union initially maintained a stance of non-involvement. It only supported North Vietnam in reconstruction efforts. However, by 1964, when the United States expanded its military operations across Vietnam, the Soviet Union began paying closer attention to the con-

flict. By late 1964, the Soviet Union permitted the National Liberation Front of South Vietnam—a resistance organization backed by North Vietnam—to establish a permanent office in Moscow. In February 1965, a high-level Soviet delegation visited Hanoi. Following this visit, the Soviet Union committed to supplying weapons to Hanoi to resist U.S. air assaults. From this point onward, the Soviet Union aimed to assert its position in Southeast Asia, while warning Vietnam not to underestimate the U.S. efforts against communism in Asia and coordinating assistance efforts with China (M.O.F.A., 1985).

In February 1965, Vietnam and the Soviet Union issued a joint communiqué affirming that the Soviet Union could not remain indifferent to the security of a fellow socialist country. The Soviet Union pledged to support and assist Vietnam, recognizing Vietnam as the outpost of socialism in Southeast Asia and emphasizing its role in fighting U.S. imperialism and contributing to world peace. Based on this stance, from 1965 to 1968, the Soviet Union provided Vietnam with 226,969 tons of military aid, valued at 1.173 billion rubles—marking the peak of Soviet assistance during the war against the U.S. In 1967, Soviet military aid to Vietnam reached its highest level, about 416 million rubles, consisting mainly of weapons and military equipment such as MiG-17, MiG-21, and IL-28 fighter aircraft, bombers, transport planes, helicopters, 6,000 anti-aircraft guns and surface-to-air missiles, 200–250 missile launchers, and thousands of various anti-aircraft weapons, along with tanks and artillery. In 1968, Soviet aid amounted to 357 million rubles, accounting for 60% of Vietnam's total external support. Additionally, the Soviet Union proposed sending to Vietnam a missile brigade, two anti-aircraft regiments, technical support units, and a MiG-21 squadron (12 fighter jets) to defend Hanoi and Hai Phong. However, Vietnam declined the deployment of these Soviet units and instead requested equipment and technical advisors (M.O.D., 2001).

Between 1969 and 1972, the Soviet Union provided Vietnam with 143,793 tons of free military aid, primarily consisting of air-defense weapons, air force equipment, tanks, and artillery—mostly new and modern—which significantly boosted the combat capability of North Vietnamese forces, especially in defending supply routes along Strategic Route 559 and achieving the "Dien Bien Phu in the Air" victory over Hanoi in December 1972. The Soviets also supplied equipment for military workshops, maintenance stations, training institutions, and research institutes (M.O.D., 2001).

The Soviet Union dispatched a large number of experts to assist the Vietnamese military. From July 1965 to December 1974, 6,359 Soviet officers and 4,500 soldiers participated in operations in Vietnam. Thirteen Soviet experts were killed in action, 2,190 Soviet military advisors received medals and decorations from the Soviet State, and over 3,000 were honored with medals and decorations from the Democratic Republic of Vietnam. Furthermore, the Soviet Union played a crucial role in training Vietnam's military personnel. Between 1965 and 1966 alone, the Soviet Union trained approximately 8,000 Vietnamese personnel

(including 2,600 in 1966) for the Air Defense and Air Force branches (M.O.D., 2001).

Several reasons drove the shift in Soviet policy toward Vietnam during the Second Indochina War. First, the U.S. expansion of the conflict directly threatened Soviet interests. Moreover, the Soviet Union recognized the shortcomings in its foreign policy under Khrushchev. The 23rd Congress of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union (March–April 1966) moved away from emphasizing peaceful coexistence as the overarching foreign policy line and elevated support for national liberation movements while emphasizing the need to resist imperialist aggression.

Another important reason was the Soviet Union's changing perception of Vietnam, viewing it as a central player in international politics directly tied to the Soviet Union's main adversaries: the United States and China. Consequently, the Soviet Union sought to exert greater influence over Vietnam's war strategies and operations. The Soviets proposed providing pilots and missile operators for Vietnam's air defense forces. It can be said that during the Second Indochina War, the Soviet Union became Vietnam's largest foreign supporter, and its contributions were pivotal to Vietnam's eventual victories. The Vietnamese Party, State, and people have always deeply valued and remembered this immense and precious assistance (Chen Jian, 1995).

After the conflict on the Indochina Peninsula, Vietnam–Russia relations were strengthened through the signing of the Treaty of Friendship and Cooperation in November 1978. When Vietnam decided to intervene in Cambodia in December 1978, Western countries sought to impose a comprehensive embargo on Vietnam. Nevertheless, Russia continued to assist Vietnam across various fields. Following the principles of socialism and mutual support in the spirit of comradeship, Russia actively helped Vietnam tackle large-scale tasks in national reconstruction, and the development of energy, metallurgy, chemical industries, machinery manufacturing, construction, geological exploration, oil and gas extraction, as well as advancements in science, education, and culture. Thanks to this support, Vietnam was able to overcome a difficult period and break through the Western blockade (M.O.F.A., 1983).

The border conflict between Vietnam and China, which erupted from February to March 1979, served as a test of the Vietnam–Russia alliance and posed an increasing threat to the Hanoi government. Amid these tensions, Russia acted by both the spirit and the letter of the Treaty of Friendship and Cooperation signed with Vietnam. The Russian government issued a statement demanding that China immediately withdraw its troops from the territory of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam and affirmed that Russia would fulfill its obligations under the Treaty. Soviet military experts present in Vietnam promptly began working alongside Vietnamese specialists. Additional personnel also started arriving from Russia. On February 19, 1979, a group of 20 advisors and specialists from major combat branches, led by Army General Gennady Obaturov, arrived in Hanoi. General Obaturov met with Vietnam's Minister of Defense Van Tien Dung, Chief of the Gen-

eral Staff Le Trong Tan, and most importantly, the General Secretary of the Communist Party of Vietnam Le Duan. He successfully persuaded the Vietnamese leadership to urgently redeploy Vietnamese army corps from Cambodia to Lang Son — both by land and by Russian An-12 aircraft. A new unit equipped with multiple BM-21 Grad rocket launchers was proposed, based on supplies from Russia. Strategic and military cargo shipments from Russia were rapidly and consistently established: over 400 tanks and infantry fighting vehicles, 400 artillery pieces and mortars, 50 BM-21 Grad launch systems, more than 100 anti-aircraft guns, 400 portable air-defense systems, 800 handheld anti-tank grenade launchers, 20 fighter jets, technical equipment, and dozens of tons of ammunition (Mosyakov, 1986). Moscow also provided Vietnam with intelligence and military supplies via sea routes controlled by the Russian Pacific Fleet (Mosyakov, 2014).

Between 1980 and 1985, Russia remained Vietnam's leading economic partner. Trade with Russia accounted for about 70% of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam's total economic exchanges. Moscow was also Vietnam's most important source of foreign aid during this period, with annual aid flows of \$1.5–2 billion, making up approximately 20% of Vietnam's state budget. The provision of military equipment and financial assistance from Russia only ended in 1985, initiated by reforms under Mikhail Gorbachev. The close cooperation between Vietnam and Russia during the Cold War preserved a positive image of Vietnam in the eyes of the Russian people. Numerous scientific research centers were established in Russia to study Southeast Asia (Karwowski, 2010).

3. OVERVIEW OF CONTEMPORARY RUSSIAN–VIETNAMESE RELATIONS FROM 1991 TO THE PRESENT

Since 1991, Russia underwent major political reforms, abolishing communism and the Communist Party, and establishing a federal republic led by a president. Vietnamese–Russian relations also experienced significant changes. In 1994, Vietnam and Russia signed the Treaty on the Basic Principles of Friendly Relations between the Socialist Republic of Vietnam and the Russian Federation. With this treaty, both sides expressed their commitment to continue strengthening and expanding long-term cooperation across political, economic–trade, scientific-technical, military-technical, cultural, and educational fields, based on principles of equality and mutual benefit, serving the interests of both nations and contributing to the development and prosperity of Southeast Asia, the Asia–Pacific region, and the world.

The Treaty on the Basic Principles of Vietnam–Russia Friendly Relations was signed as Russia was undergoing major adjustments and turning points in its foreign policy. Russia adopted the "Eurasian Orientation" (balancing both its Western and Eastern relations) to overcome its previous one-sided focus on the United States and Western countries while placing greater emphasis on cooperation with Asia–Pacific nations, especially the CIS countries, China, India, and ASEAN.

This new foreign policy direction was emphasized by the Russian President in his State of the Nation address to the State Duma on February 24, 1994: "In 1994, we must put an end to the habit of making unilateral concessions... Russia is not a guest in Europe but a full-fledged participant in the European community and is entitled to enjoy its benefits. We shall proceed from this premise" (Manh, 2022). In implementing its "Eurasian Orientation," Russia increasingly turned its attention to Southeast Asia, recognizing the region's significant post-Cold War transformations, particularly the improved relations between Indochinese countries and ASEAN. The region's dynamic development also led Russia to revise its approach toward ASEAN and adjust its policy accordingly. Expanding bilateral relations with individual ASEAN countries, Russia made notable efforts to develop multilateral ties with ASEAN, especially after becoming one of the 18 members of the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF) in April 1994, and one of ASEAN's ten full dialogue partners by July 1996 (Manh, 2022).

Vietnam–Russia political relations have maintained a high level of trust and have continued to grow stronger. High-level exchanges have taken place frequently, providing strong momentum for the development of their comprehensive partnership. In 1997, during his visit to Hanoi, Russian Prime Minister Viktor Chernomyrdin affirmed that Vietnam was considered Moscow's strategic partner. Another important high-level visit occurred in August 1998 when President Tran Duc Luong visited Moscow. In his meeting with Boris Yeltsin, the leaders established permanent diplomatic channels and expressed their willingness to cooperate within regional and international frameworks. Thanks to the warming relationship, Vietnam supported Russia's stance on actions in Chechnya, while Russia adopted a more neutral language regarding the South China Sea disputes. Political cooperation also paved the way for increased investments in strategic sectors such as energy and raw material extraction. In the 1990s, the Vietsovpetro joint venture, active in Vietnam since 1981, operated very successfully. By 2000, the company was responsible for 80% of Vietnam's crude oil production, making it a major player in the regional energy resource market (Pietrasiak, 2002). Since 2008, Vietnam and Russia have established an annual strategic dialogue mechanism on diplomacy, defense, and security. Both sides have also conducted regular political consultations at the deputy foreign minister and departmental levels, within the framework of cooperation between the two Ministries of Foreign Affairs (Manh, 2022).

In 2013, President Vladimir Putin made a state visit to Vietnam. In his speech during this high-level visit, Putin affirmed that Vietnam is one of Moscow's most important partners. Russia's pivot to Asia led to more frequent high-level visits between leaders in Hanoi and Moscow. When President Truong Tan Sang visited Sochi on July 27 of the same year, the relationship was elevated to a Comprehensive Strategic Partnership. A return visit took place in November. Politicians mainly addressed the impact of the financial crisis and the need to build a new, multipolar world order. In

2015, Vietnam signed a Free Trade Agreement with the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU), which came into effect in November of the following year. This step was seen as Hanoi's willingness to engage in multilateral economic initiatives that benefit Russia's foreign policy strategy.

In terms of defense and security cooperation, Russia has always been Vietnam's most important partner. In 1993, Vietnam purchased its first six Su-27 fighter jets from Russia, and in 1995, Hanoi imported another six (Buszyński, 2006). Around the same period, Vietnam also imported six Project 1241RE Corvette ships (Molniya/Tarantul class) from Moscow, enhancing the capabilities of the Vietnam People's Navy. Cam Ranh Military Port was leased to Russia to serve as the base for the 17th Operational Squadron of the Pacific Fleet starting in 1979. Russia expanded Cam Ranh, building fuel and ammunition storage facilities, barracks, and developing capabilities to accommodate nuclear submarines. Personnel numbers, initially estimated at around 5,000 before 1989, were halved by the 1990s. The Russian military withdrew in May 2002 (Rogozińska, Olech, 2020).

According to Hiep (2013), the most critical aspect of Vietnam–Russia bilateral relations is defense cooperation. Russia was Vietnam's largest arms supplier, accounting for over 80% of Vietnam's arms imports between 1990 and 2010. Just five days before President Putin's visit, Russia delivered the first of six Kilo-class submarines under a \$2 billion procurement contract signed in 2009. Other notable Russian arms transfers to Vietnam included 20 Su-30MK fighter jets, two Gepard-3 frigates, and two K-300P Bastion-P coastal defense missile systems. During President Putin's visit, the two countries also signed a military cooperation agreement to formalize their defense partnership. Military cooperation was further enhanced with the signing of a memorandum of understanding in October 2008. Russia sought to leverage market opportunities in rapidly developing Vietnam and the transportation routes connecting Vietnam to Russia's Far East. Russian arms sales to Vietnam quickly became a central element of the strategic partnership. Between 2008 and 2012, the Vietnam People's Navy received two Gepard-class guided-missile frigates and four Svetlyak-class fast patrol boats. The Navy also acquired 40 Yakhont/SS-N-26 anti-ship missiles and 400 Kh-35 Uran/SS-N-25 anti-ship missiles. In 2009, Vietnam signed a contract to purchase six advanced conventional submarines under the Project 636 Varshavyanka (Kilo-class) series. The Vietnamese Air Defense and Air Force received 20 Su-30MK2V fighter jets equipped with Kh-59MK anti-ship cruise missiles, 100 R-73 (AA-11 Archer) short-range air-to-air missiles, 200 9M311/SA-19 Grison surface-to-air missiles, two S-300PMU-1 surface-to-air missile systems, four Kolchuga air-defense radar systems, and three VERA passive radar systems. Vietnam also received two K-300P Bastion coastal defense missile complexes. On July 27, 2012, President Putin and President Sang met in the resort city of Sochi and issued a Joint Declaration elevating their bilateral relations to a Comprehensive Strategic Partnership. Russia's arms

sales and defense services to Vietnam have since become the most critical aspect of their bilateral relationship. Since 2012, Vietnam has ordered an additional 12 Su-30MK2 fighter jets and two Gepard 3.9-class frigates designed for anti-submarine warfare. Russia was also awarded a contract to build a military ship maintenance and repair facility at Cam Ranh Bay. On the eve of Putin's visit to Vietnam in November, Russia transported Vietnam's first Kilo-class submarine and announced that it would hand over a submarine crew training center under construction at Cam Ranh Bay by January 2014. At the end of Putin's visit that month, a Joint Statement was issued, briefly mentioning a defense cooperation agreement without providing details. Media reports and official statements indicated that Russia would be deeply involved in the maintenance of military equipment sold to Vietnam and would transfer military technologies for licensed production. For instance, Vietnam and Russia will likely collaborate in the licensed production of the Uran (SS-N-25 Switchblade) anti-ship missile. In an interview on November 9, ahead of Putin's visit, Vietnamese President Truong Tan Sang proposed that the two countries "enhance military cooperation to a new level" and create a "new breakthrough" in their comprehensive strategic partnership. He also suggested "joint ventures for production, research, establishing service centers and after-sales services, as well as exports to third countries." President Putin, in a statement before arriving in Hanoi, noted that military and technical cooperation had entered an entirely new phase. No longer limited to exports, efforts were being made to initiate licensed production of advanced military equipment with the support of Russian companies in Vietnam. In December 2009, an agreement was signed for the construction of six Varshavyanka-class (Kilo-class) submarines for Vietnam at Russian shipyards. This was one of the largest contracts in their bilateral military relations and was completed in February 2014 with the launch of the final vessel. In 2009, two K-300P Bastion-P systems were purchased from Russia, and the delivery terms for eight Su-30MK2 aircraft were agreed upon. A year later, a contract was signed to import an additional 12 fighter jets. In 2013, Vietnam purchased 12 more Su-30MK2 aircraft and two Gepard-class frigates, which were delivered in 2016 and 2017 (Thayer, 2013).

According to Phuong (2015), from Hanoi's perspective, Russia remains Vietnam's largest arms supplier and the main source of military technology transfer, a relationship that dates back to the Cold War era. Meanwhile, the United States only partially lifted its arms embargo against Vietnam in 2012. Many Vietnamese officials who fought against the United States during the war view Moscow as having helped train generations of Vietnamese leaders and supported Hanoi through decades of international isolation. For this reason, Vietnamese officials are unlikely to push Russia aside, even as they embrace partnerships with the West and pursue free trade agreements such as the Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP). Hanoi remained publicly silent after Washington privately expressed concerns over Russia's use of Cam Ranh Bay, and when the matter became public a few days later.

In November 2014, during the visit of General Secretary of the Communist Party of Vietnam Nguyen Phu Trong to Sochi, the rules governing the use of the Cam Ranh military base were formalized. Russian vessels were only required to provide advance notice before entering the bay, while units from other countries were permitted access only once a year (Phuong, 2015). At the same time, Vietnam asserted that, under its foreign policy doctrine, it would maintain full control over the Cam Ranh base. This agreement was reached amid escalating tensions between Russia and the West following the occupation of Eastern Ukraine and Crimea. Consequently, Moscow increased its air operations in the Asia-Pacific region. With access to Cam Ranh, Russian forces were able to refuel their Tu-95 bombers, conducting flights near American facilities and bases. In 2016, Vietnam signed a contract with Russia to purchase 64 T-90 tanks, a deal completed in 2019. In January 2020, Hanoi authorities decided to buy 12 Yak-130 jet trainers and light combat aircraft for \$350 million. Experts interpreted this contract as a precursor to the future acquisition of SU-35 fighter jets and potentially even fifth-generation SU-57 aircraft. According to Storey (2021), Vietnam topped the list of Southeast Asian countries purchasing Russian weaponry. Within the region, Southeast Asian countries can be divided into three main groups: long-time customers (Vietnam, Malaysia, Myanmar, Indonesia, and Laos); new and potential customers (Thailand, the Philippines, and Cambodia); and countries with low potential (Singapore and Brunei).

In January 2018, Vietnamese Minister of Defense Ngo Xuan Lich met with his Russian counterpart Sergei Shoigu in Hanoi. The two ministers agreed on the need to enhance the sharing of perspectives on defense and security issues of mutual concern, and to further strengthen cooperation in traditional areas, including military-technical collaboration, based on equality and mutual benefit. Vietnam expressed its support for the Russian Federation's efforts to expand defense relations with ASEAN countries, particularly Russia's active participation in ASEAN-led regional security mechanisms. Vietnam and Russia signed a plan for the development of bilateral defense cooperation for the 2018–2020 period. This document aimed to implement the previously signed defense cooperation agreement and to establish a three-year roadmap to deepen and make their defense partnership more effective and substantive.

According to Manh (2022), the strengthening of high-level military delegation exchanges has bolstered strategic trust between the armed forces of Vietnam and the Russian Federation. This trust serves as a foundation for the effective implementation of various areas of cooperation, including the exchange of strategic perspectives; personnel training; the improvement of the cooperation framework; collaboration between military branches (navy, air force, engineering, chemical units, etc.); military-technical cooperation; scientific research within the framework of the Vietnam-Russia Tropical Center; military medicine; United Nations peacekeeping efforts; cooperation at multilateral forums; military

competitions; and military cultural and artistic exchanges. Since the Ministries of Defense of the two countries signed the agreement on defense cooperation and the framework contract for training cooperation (2009–2019), defense cooperation has continued to be actively promoted, yielding significant results in fields such as: officer training, information and communications work, professional experience sharing in logistics, military cartography, military prosecution, and military science. In particular, following the implementation of the agreement between the General Department of Political Affairs of the Vietnam People's Army and the Main Directorate for Ideological Work of the Ministry of Defense of Belarus signed in June 2012, and the visit of Major General Aleksandr Nikolaevich, Head of the Directorate, to Vietnam in October 2014, both sides organized working delegations to exchange experience in journalism and television. Further consultations took place in the first half of February 2021. In December 2021, an agreement was signed to expand the declining volume of arms and technology trade. This event occurred on the sidelines of a visit to Moscow by a Vietnamese delegation led by President Nguyen Xuan Phuc (Thuy, 2021).

Since 2022, Russia has launched a "special military operation" in Ukraine, allocating significant resources to the conflict. Nevertheless, the traditional relationship between Moscow and Hanoi has remained strong. Vietnam did not condemn Russia's invasion in February 2022, even though it recognizes the prohibition of the use of force and the threat against other nations as a core principle of its national security policy — a principle outlined in its 2019 Defense White Paper (Grossman, 2022). Vietnam abstained from voting on two United Nations General Assembly resolutions condemning the invasion and voted against suspending Russia's membership in the United Nations Human Rights Council. An ideological connection also binds the two countries, underscored by the agreement between the Communist Party of Vietnam and Russia's ruling United Russia party. Despite Hanoi's increasingly close ties with the Western world, there remains a certain degree of suspicion and fear regarding support for democratic transitions — changes that the Communist Party of Vietnam is determined to avoid. These close ties were further demonstrated through the meeting between Foreign Minister Sergei Lavrov and his Vietnamese counterpart Bui Thanh Son in Hanoi in July 2022. Lavrov was also received by General Secretary of the Communist Party Nguyen Phu Trong and Prime Minister Pham Minh Chinh, further emphasizing the importance of the visit. Moreover, in April of this year, Russian media reported — despite signs of cooling from Vietnam — that the two countries were planning to conduct joint military exercises titled "Continental Alliance – 2022" (Hai, 2022).

In December 2024, General Alexander Vasilyevich Fomin and a delegation from the Russian Ministry of Defense visited Vietnam to attend the 7th Vietnam-Russia Defense Strategic Dialogue. On this occasion, the Vietnamese Minister of National Defense extended warm greetings to his Russian counterpart, Andrey Removich Belousov, through General Fomin.

Vietnamese defense leaders reaffirmed that the people and the People's Army of Vietnam deeply value and appreciate Russia's significant support during Vietnam's struggle for national independence and reunification, as well as in the country's current efforts toward development and national defense. The Ministry of Defense and the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation sent a delegation to participate in the 80th anniversary of the founding of the Vietnam People's Army, the 35th anniversary of the All-People National Defense Day, and the Vietnam Defense Expo 2024. The participation of leading Russian defense enterprises played a key role in the event's overall success. During the event, both sides exchanged views on global and regional issues of mutual concern, reviewed achievements in defense cooperation, identified key directions for future collaboration, and signed several important documents. Vietnamese Defense Minister Phan Van Giang proposed that both sides continue to advance defense cooperation in line with the traditional friendship and the Comprehensive Strategic Partnership between Vietnam and Russia. This cooperation should be based on international law, each country's foreign policy, legal frameworks, and Vietnam's practical conditions.

4. CONCLUSION

Originating as a strategic ally during the Indochina War, the Soviet Union provided Vietnam with crucial military aid, including weapons, equipment, and supplies. These substantial contributions enabled Vietnam to adopt modern warfare tactics, giving it the capability to stand up against powerful imperialist forces such as France and the United States. This support, when combined with Vietnam's internal strength, created a powerful synergy known as the "combination of national strength and the spirit of the times," ultimately leading to Vietnam's victory over both global powers. The Soviet military assistance was rooted in the spirit of proletarian internationalism, driven by the shared goal of fighting a common enemy and building a better society. The success of the Indochina War, facilitated by Soviet support, not only elevated the Soviet Union's global standing but also solidified the long-lasting Vietnam–Soviet Union relationship. Over the past three decades, as the Russian Federation emerged as Vietnam's strategic partner, military cooperation has become a key pillar in Vietnam–Russia relations. Vietnam remains a crucial market for Russian arms exports. The Vietnamese government has invested heavily in acquiring modern Russian weaponry, such as missile systems, naval vessels, and aircraft, and in sending Vietnamese officers for military training in Russia. These imports have accelerated the modernization of the Vietnamese military and enhanced the country's defense capabilities in the face of regional instability, particularly in relation to the South China Sea disputes. Defense cooperation with Russia continues to offer significant benefits to Vietnam, especially as Russia's defense industry remains a prominent player on the international stage.

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